

A Study of the Functional Outcome of Distal Both Bone Leg Fractures Treated with Tip Locking Interlocking Nailing and Fibular Plating

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Abstract:

Background: Intramedullary nail fixation remains the treatment of choice of unstable and displaced tibial shaft fractures in adults. The goals of treatment are to achieve osseous union and to restore length, alignment and rotation of the fractured tibia. The implant offers appropriate biomechanics fracture stabilisation and acts as a load sharing device allowing early postoperative mobilisation. Recent advances in nail design and reduction techniques have expanded the indications for intramedullary nail fixation to include distal third tibial fractures.

Materials and Methods: A prospective observational study based on 100 cases of distal both bone leg fractures admitted and treated surgically in Orthopaedic wards of Government Medical College Trivandrum for a period of 1yr during the study period. Data was collected using structured pro forma, questionnaire and functional outcome analysed based on American Orthopaedic Foot and Ankle Score. The axis of the leg was studied using Paley and Tets worth method on post-operative X-rays.

Results: The study included 101 patients with distal both bone leg fractures who fulfilled the criteria. The age of the patients ranged from 18 years to 67 years, the largest age group was 21 years to 30 years 34.9% of patients. Males (77%) were predominant in our study. Most had right sided involvement (62%). The study had about 63% closed fractures. Patients were treated based on hospital protocol and were followed up at 6 weeks 12 weeks and at 6 months for clinical and radiological evaluation. Assessment of functional outcome was done using American Orthopaedic Foot and Ankle Society score after attaining weight bearing. The mean AOFAS score was 77.15 (Range of 45 to 100). The mean score in males was 77.35 and in females was slightly lower at 76.47. Closed fractures showed better mean score of 84.68 while open fractures had a mean score of 64.13. The average time taken to partial weight bearing was 7 weeks (range of 3 weeks to 16 weeks). The average time taken to full weight bearing was 11 weeks (range of 6 weeks to 20 weeks). The average time taken to return to work was 16 weeks (range of 8 weeks to 25 weeks). Out of the 101 patients, 12 patients have changed their job or have not returned to their job since they were not able to continue in their previous jobs due to their injury. The rest of the patients were able to return to their previous jobs without any difficulties. The radiological parameters revealed that 5 of the 101 patients had a varus deformity in the immediate postop X- ray. The average varus angle according to the Paley and Tets worth method was found to be 5.5 degrees (Range of 0-11 degrees). 6 patients had fixation in valgus with the average valgus angle being 8.5 degrees (Range 0-17 degrees). The X- rays revealed 4 patients with more than 10 degrees of recurvatum angle by Paley and Tets worth method in lateral Xrays. All four had higher recurvatum angles than the immediate post op period indicating a loss of reduction or malalignment. The average recurvatum angle in the final follow up x-rays were 4.56 degrees (Range of 0 to 16.5 degrees). In the follow up examination where the minimal follow up period was 6 months, wound healing was 96%. 1 patient was excluded because of wound infection. He sustained an open fracture (Gustilo 3B) for which he underwent intramedullary nailing with fibular fixation. During followup his wound infection did not resolve with antibiotics. Hence 3 months post-op he underwent nail exit and ortho fix fixation. 4 patients underwent additional procedures. Mostly for their soft tissue cover in the form of split thickness skin grafting except for one patient who underwent bone grafting in addition to skin grafting for a metaphyseal bone loss 1 month after the intramedullary nailing.

Conclusion: From our study we conclude that intramedullary nailing of distal both leg fractures along with fibular plating allowed early mobilization of knee joint with excellent functional outcome. The AOFAS performed well in assessing the functional outcome. Functional outcome mainly depended upon the type of

injury with closed fractures showing significantly better scores than open fractures. Functional outcome was not related to age or sex of the patient. Complications like malalignment are present with nailing of distal third tibial fractures even though it is a universally accepted modality of treatment.

Keywords: AOFAS, Tibial, Metaphyseal, Nailing, Skin grafting, Recurvatum angle.

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Introduction

The tibial shaft is the commonest site of long bone fractures due to its superficial location. Tibial shaft fractures usually involve young or middle age people. The rapid growth of technology and urbanisation has led to enormous growth of new vehicles on road. [1,2] This has led to increase in road traffic injuries and deaths. Globally the number of deaths in major road traffic accidents is estimated at 1.2million deaths /year while the number injured is as high as 50 million injuries /yr. [3] Fractures of the distal tibial third are different in that the bone is subcutaneous with no muscle covering in the anteromedial aspect and consequently with less blood supply. This precarious blood supply may lead to delayed union or nonunion. [4,5] Treatment remains a major substantial therapeutic challenge in orthopaedic trauma, considering its anatomy, it is difficult to achieve and maintain reduction owing to wide metaphysis, bad skin condition and fracture comminution.

In addition, it is more difficult if fibular fractures are present at the same level, which contribute to additional mechanical instability and syndesmotic injury if the fracture is present at the lower 10cm. In India, more than 4,37,396 lives are lost due to road traffic accidents every year (WHO global safety report 2019). [6] According to the WHO Report, road traffic injuries were ranked as the ninth cause of death in all and ranked as fourth cause of death. In India it is ranked as 6th leading cause of death. A 4.4-fold increase has been detected in the number of road traffic accidents between the years 1970- 2018. Subsequently the number of deaths has increased by 9.8 folds and the number of injuries by 7.3 folds. [7] To note is that one third of fatalities in India involve the pedestrians and two wheelers who are called as the 'vulnerable road users'. Under developed and developing countries account for 91.8% of DALY's lost to road traffic injuries worldwide. It was in 1969 the treatment of distal tibia fractures got revolutionised by the study done by Reudi and Allgower where 74% of patients after surgery were pain free with good functional outcome at 4 years' follow-up. Therefore, in 1970's and 80's widespread use of internal fixation for distal tibia fractures became popular. However, this was also accompanied by a high rate of major complications like malunion 42%, superficial infections 20%, and

non-union in 18% and osteomyelitis in 17%. These high rates of complications emphasised the importance in handling soft tissues during fracture management. But all these fractures in Reudi and Allgower series were low energy injuries. They published another series in 1979 which consisted of high energy injuries and found that overall results were not good. [8,9] This led to methods which caused less soft tissue damage and yielded better results. The new techniques used were Intra Medullary nailing (IM nailing), hybrid fixators and biological minimally invasive plate osteosynthesis (MIPO). The major goal in the treatment of fracture tibia is achieving functionally useful and stable extremity. Yet the spectrum of injuries to tibia is so great that no single method of treatment is applicable to all fractures. Intramedullary interlocking nailing is a technique which allows stable reduction, maintenance of reduction and allows early mobilisation. Intramedullary interlocking nail is advantageous over other surgical methods as it preserves the soft-tissue sleeve around the fracture site, the periosteum is not disturbed, and being a closed procedure there is no disturbance of fracture hematoma, with less incidence of infection. The ability to lock the nails proximally and distally provides control of length, alignment, and rotation in unstable fractures and permits stabilisation of fractures located below the tibial tubercle or 3 to 4 cm proximal to the ankle joint. [10] Complications like long period of immobilisation, incidence of muscle wasting and stiffness of joint due to treatment with plaster immobilisation and external fixator application is reduced with the use of intramedullary interlocking nail.

Materials and Methods

Study design: Prospective observational study.

Study setting: Orthopaedic wards of Government Medical College, Thiruvananthapuram.

Study period: Maximum of one year after IEC approval has obtained.

Source of data: The study was conducted on patients with distal both bone leg fractures treated by tip locking interlocking nailing and fibular plating in the Department of Orthopaedics, Government Medical College Thiruvananthapuram.

Inclusion Criteria

- All patients above 17 years of age
- Both gender
- Having Gustillo's Grade I or II open fracture
- Close fracture of the distal diaphysis of the tibia and fibula was chosen for the reamed interlocking nailing.
- Patients who sustained extrarticular distal both bone fractures from 4cms – 11cms above the tibial plafond treated by intramedullary interlocking nailing and fibular plating will be included in the study.
- Both open and closed fractures were included.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with pathological fractures, stress fractures, paediatric patients (< 17 yrs of age), metabolic bone diseases, distal tibia fractures with intra-articular involvement, isolated tibial fractures, extra-articular fractures involved in other interventional studies and Gustillo-Anderson Grade 3 fractures were excluded.

Study observations

- Age distribution
- Gender distribution
- Side of injury
- Mode of injury
- Open or closed fracture
- Radiographic assessment was done comparing the anteroposterior and lateral views of the affected leg with both the knee and ankle joints included. The varus/valgus angles were calculated by the Paley and Tets worth method. Lines were drawn horizontally over the tibial plateau and tibial plafond. Their midpoints were identified and connected with a vertical line. Then a perpendicular was drawn to the horizontal line over the tibial plafond. The angle formed between the perpendicular and line joining the midpoints of the plateau and plafond was considered as the varus/valgus angle based on lateral or medial angulation respectively.
- AOFAS: The American orthopaedic Foot and Ankle Society Score (AOFAS) introduced by Kitaoka et al in 1994.

It has nine questions divided into three components. Pain, Function, Alignment Total score possible for a patient was 100 points. Alignment of the foot and range of motion of the ankle (measured by orthopaedic goniometer) was completed by the examiner on clinical assessment and assessing the radiographs. The other questions were completed by the patients. The individual scores were then added together to obtain an overall functional score, which was then expressed as a percentage of the normal (100 points).

Surgical Methods

Surgical procedures were performed by either a consultant or a post-graduate. In all cases surgery was performed in supine position. The injured limb was painted and draped in such a way that it can be left freely hanging down from the side of the operating table. It was ensured that adequate flexion of the knee was possible to achieve central placement of the guide wire without hitting the posterior cortex. Fibular fixation was done after passing guide wire into distal tibial fragment for easiness of reduction. Incision was put over midline of knee from lower pole of patella to tibial tuberosity. Patellar tendon splitting approach was used for all cases. Entry awl is introduced medial to lateral tibial spine upto medullary cavity.

The guide wire was introduced through the entry and the fracture was reduced and kept in alignment. The guide wire is then manoeuvred through to the distal fragment. The tibia is then serially reamed by 1mm increments from 8mm to maximum possible diameter. The nails available in our centre were 8mm, 9mm, and 10mm. The tibia is usually reamed 1mm more than the size of the nail to be inserted. Following reaming, the leg is placed on top of the table with the guide wire inside and clamped outside to the drape. Then fibula is fixed with lateral approach. Fractures are reduced and fixed by 1/3rd tubular plates or 3.5mm DCP. The wound is closed and the leg is then hanged again from the side to insert the nail. All nails were locked by two distal and two proximal locking bolts. No drains are used. Wound is closed in normal fashion

Postoperative care

Antibiotic prophylaxis in the peri-operative period included intravenous Cefuroxime and Gentamicin for closed fractures. All intravenous antibiotics were continued for 2 days and was started on oral antibiotics for another 5 days. The duration of IV antibiotics was longer on an average upto 10 days (range 5-15 days) if it was a case of open fracture. The patients were discharged from the ward once they were comfortable. They were started on toe-touch weight bearing or non-weight bearing crutch walking as the fracture pattern demanded and were followed up in OPD at regular intervals at 6 weeks, 3 months, 6 months' interval.

Statistical analysis

The data was expressed in number, percentage, mean and standard deviation. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 20.0) version used for analysis. Chi square test applied to find the statistical significant. p value less than 0.05 considered statistically significant at 95% confidence interval.

Results

We studied 101 patients with distal both bone leg who were managed surgically by tip locking interlocking nailing and fibular plating in our department. The following are the observations made and the available data are analysed as follows. One patient had infection during the course of follow up and hence underwent an implant exit followed by ortho fix fixation. He was not included for functional outcome assessment. Males predominated in our study. Out of 101 patients 78 were male and remaining 23 patients was female. In our study out of 101 patients 63 had right sided injury and 38 had left sided injury. Open injuries accounted for about 63% of the floating knee injuries. The duration of the procedures ranged from 60 minutes to 140 minutes. The fixation of the fibula required 40-50 minutes while reaming, insertion of the nail and locking required another 40-60 minutes. The mean time required was 1 hour and 35 minutes. All cases were done after reaming the tibial medullary cavity. The radiological parameters revealed that 5 of the 101 patients had a varus deformity in the immediate postop X- ray. The average varus angle according to the Paley and Tets worth method was found to be 5.5 degrees (Range of 0-11 degrees). 6 patients had fixation in valgus with the average valgus angle being 8.5 degrees (Range 0-17 degrees). The X- rays revealed 4 patients with more than 10 degrees of procurvatum/recurvatum angle. All four had higher procurvatum/recurvatum angles than the immediate post op period indicating a loss of reduction or malalignment. The average procurvatum/recurvatum angle in the final follow up x-rays were 4.56 degrees (Range of 0 to 16.5 degrees) (Table-1). The mean AOFAS score was 77.15 (Range of 45 to 100). The mean score in males was 77.35 and in females was slightly lower at 76.47. Closed fractures showed better mean score of 84.68 while open fractures had a mean score of 64.13. The average time taken to partial weight bearing was 7 weeks (range of 3 weeks to 16 weeks). The average time taken to full weight bearing was 11 weeks (range of 6 weeks to 20

weeks). The average time taken to return to work was 16 weeks (range of 8 weeks to 25 weeks). Out of the 101 patients, 12 patients have changed their job or have not returned to their job since they were not able to continue in their previous jobs due to their injury. The rest of the patients were able to return to their previous jobs without any difficulties, in the follow up examination where the minimal follow up period was 6 months, wound healing was 96%. 1 patient was excluded because of wound infection. He sustained an open fracture (Gustilo 3B) for which he underwent intramedullary nailing with fibular fixation. During follow up his wound infection did not resolve with antibiotics. Hence 3 months' post-op he underwent nail exit and orthofix fixation. 4 patients underwent additional procedures. Mostly for their soft tissue cover in the form of split thickness skin grafting except for one patient who underwent bone grafting in addition to skin grafting for a metaphyseal bone loss 1 month after the intramedullary nailing. 32 yr old male with alleged history of road traffic accident, high energy injury, sustained an open fracture Gustilo type 1 to the left lower limb. The fracture was classified as AO type 43 A1.1. (Graph-1). The fracture was stabilised with tip locking nail for the tibia and closed reduction and internal fixation with plate and screws by MIPPO for the fibula. He did not have any angulation. His AOFAS score was excellent. He started partial weight bearing at 5 weeks and full weight bearing at 9 weeks. Return to work was at 12 weeks (Image-1, Case-1). 66 years old male with alleged history of road traffic accident, high energy injury, sustained an open fracture Gustilo type 2 to the left lower limb. The fracture was classified as AO type 43 A 2.3. The fracture was stabilised with tip locking nail for the tibia and open reduction and internal fixation with plate and screws for the fibula. He had valgus angulation of 15 degrees. His AOFAS score was fair at 55 out of 100. He started partial weight bearing at 9 weeks and full weight bearing at 12 weeks. Return to work was at 16 weeks. Dynamisation was done at 12 weeks (Image-2, Case-2).

Table 1: Distribution of patients based on demographic data

Demographic data	Number	Percentage (%)
Age		
Less than 20	8	7.90
21-30	35	34.60
31-40	29	28.70
41-50	14	13.80
More than 50	15	14.80
Gender		
Male	78	77.22
Female	23	22.73
Side of injury		
Right	63	62.37

Left	38	37.63
AOFAS overall grading		
BAD (<50)	3	2.97
Moderate (51-70)	25	24.75
Good (71-90)	65	64.35
Maximum	10	9.90

Graph 1: Distribution of patients based on open and closed injuries

Case-1:

Figure 1:

Case-2:**Figure 2:****Discussion**

The functional outcomes assessed, when analysed, revealed the fact that worse functional outcomes were not related with age or sex. It was associated with the type of injury associated with the fracture. Closed fractures showed significantly better scores than open fractures.

Patients with malalignment showed relatively poor scores. This explains the need for perfect alignment of fracture intra-operatively to achieve better functional outcomes. [11] The overall patient satisfaction is always related to improved physical function and ability to return to work.

This applies to population all over the world. In Indian population particularly patients and their dependants are more eager to know on their time to return to job or functional normality than knowing the type of treatment they are going to receive. [12] In this context our study has showed a mean time to return to work as 16 weeks (4 months).

This is comparatively less time when considering both open and closed tibial fractures. Earlier studies and literature have given an average of 5 months 'time to return to work of patients who underwent nailing for distal tibia fractures. It has also been reported that nearly 95 % of patients have returned to their work post distal tibia fractures no matter what the type of fixation was. Out of which 70 %

had returned to moderate to heavy jobs which they were previously performing before the injury. The AOFAS score has performed well in estimating the functional outcome in our study. Women had scores comparable to men. This was in contradiction to the Valliers study in 2011 where functional scores of women were poor. [13]

The incidence of implant related pain in our study is 30 %. The literature gives a 16% incidence of implant exit after tibia nailing in distal tibia fractures. Fibular fracture fixation done along with nailing helped in reducing common angular deviation like valgus at fracture site to 6 patients. It also helped in increasing fracture fixation stability. Varus deformity was seen in 5 patients in whom the tibial nail was not aligned in the centre of the medullary cavity.

This issues of malalignment could have been corrected by use of Poller screws which was not done due to non-availability of image intensifier in our emergency operation theatre. It also showed that alignment should be carefully checked during the procedure to reduce the rate of malalignment. [14] There should be more studies on the use of fibula fixation and Poller screw use to determine their role in distal tibia fracture fixation. The amount of malalignment considered as malunion in the diagnostic criteria in this study is controversial. But the recommendation by Trafton (acceptable

malalignment is < 5 degrees of varus-valgus angulation, there was definitively a recall bias on when partial weight bearing was started and when full weight bearing was started. [15]

Conclusion

Intramedullary nailing of distal both leg fractures along with fibular plating allowed early mobilization of knee joint with excellent functional outcome. The AOFAS performed well in assessing the functional outcome. Functional outcome mainly depended upon the type of injury with closed fractures showing significantly better scores than open fractures. Functional outcome was not related to age or sex of the patient. Complications like malalignment are present with nailing of distal third tibial fractures even though it is a universally accepted modality of treatment.

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